

Supplementary Figure 11. Chord diagram showing the DEGs found to associate with several selected GO categories (on the right) for chitosan-treated WT adult plants, in comparison to mock treated WT. The color code of the fold change of genes' expression is shown on the right.

Supplementary Figure 14. Chord diagram showing the DEGs found to associate with several selected GO categories (on the right) for chitosan-treated *exo70B1xB2* adult plants, in comparison to mock treated *exo70B1xB2*. The color code of the fold change of genes' expression is shown on the right.